

ADAPTIVE NEUROPLASTICITY ASSOCIATED WITH ISCHEMIC BRAIN DAMAGE AND ITS ROLE IN STROKE RECOVERY: THEORETICAL PREREQUISITES FOR EFFECTIVE NEUROREHABILITATION

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Ischemic brain damage, like other pathogenic factors, initiates the reorganization of cortical centers and pathways outside the "nuclear zone" of acute or chronic ischemia, which limits the spontaneous restoration of functions in victims. Accordingly, knowledge of the basic patterns of post-ischemic neuroplastic remodeling is crucial for developing more effective rehabilitation strategies for stroke patients. The article discusses modern concepts of neuroplasticity: the main patterns of post-stroke reorganization of the central nervous system, studied in rodents, as well as clinical markers of compensatory and regenerative processes in conditions of chronic cerebral ischemia in cerebrovascular diseases, which allows us to identify the mechanisms underlying the remodeling of neural networks in the penumbra and contralateral hemisphere against the background of ischemic damage. At the same time, the analysis of electrophysiological experimental data demonstrated the restructuring of functional connections in both hemispheres far beyond the focus of cerebral infarction, and clinical and biochemical studies on the model of chronic cerebral ischemia in patients helped to identify key trophic factors determining compensatory and regenerative processes. The results obtained make it possible to justify the use of noninvasive brain stimulation methods and some pharmacological agents to accelerate the recovery of impaired functions in patients with this profile, and therefore to form rehabilitation protocols using robotic devices to promote the development of adaptive neuroplasticity and full-fledged functional recovery.

In this regard, it seems relevant to analyze the results of recent experimental and clinical studies that have studied the processes of neuroplasticity in ischemic brain lesions in order to develop and implement new rehabilitation strategies.

The term "brain plasticity" or "neuroplasticity" defines all (morphological and functional) changes in neural networks and glial complexes that occur in the

central nervous system throughout a person's life [9]. These changes are not only closely related to the mechanisms of learning, development, aging, and adaptation to the environment, but also underlie adaptive neuroplasticity – compensatory and regenerative reactions that occur during the formation of pathomorphological and/or functional disorders caused by diseases or injuries of the nervous system [10]. In particular, acute ischemia and chronic ischemia cause multilevel (in the cerebral cortex, the penumbra zone of the affected hemisphere and the contralateral hemisphere, subcortical and cerebrospinal regions) neuroplastic reactions of neural networks with temporal and spatial organization (Figure) [11, 12], and these changes are sensitive to subsequent damage regardless of their nature [13, 14].

The degree and range of neuroplastic changes depend on the size and rate of formation of ischemic brain damage (acute or chronic). In microinfarcts developing in the cerebral cortex against the background of transient ischemic attacks or chronic cerebral ischemia caused, for example, by small vessel disease, periinfarction zones can compensate for lost functions in the shortest possible time, which explains the existence of "mute" strokes [1, 2]. This is especially true of the ventral premotor region, which, being in close relationship with the primary motor cortex, produces and releases vascular endothelial growth factor, which has angiogenic and neuroprotective properties in the early period after a heart attack [12]. In rodents, after a stroke, there is a steady reorganization of the motor map of the rostral zone of representation of the forelimbs (premotor cortex) [2, 3, 4]. Accordingly, the development of secondary post-ischemic metabolic disorders in it exacerbates the primary motor deficit [5].

The mechanisms underlying cortical reorganization and restoration of impaired functions remain not fully understood [1]. This is especially true of the gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) system and neuroglia, which may play an important role in the control of neuroplastic reactions. So far, it has been established that the neuroglial matrix, which consists of condensed chondroitin sulfate proteoglycans surrounding mainly the bodies of GABAergic neurons, correlates according to the feedback principle with adaptive neuroplasticity and repair of the brain due to interneurons containing parvalbumin [6]. The significance of perineuronal networks has been thoroughly investigated during the maturation of the visual system. They have been found to have a stabilizing effect on mature neural networks and a negative effect on neuroplasticity [7, 8]. Thus, inhibition of perineuronal networks by injections of the bacterial enzyme

chondroitinase ABC after damage to the central nervous system accelerated the restoration of sensorimotor functions [3-4], and a spontaneous decrease in the number of perineuronal networks in the cortex in the penumbra area indicated an increase in adaptive neuroplasticity [23]. In turn, increased GABAergic activity after stroke did not improve recovery rates [2], but rather worsened motor deficits [4]. Moreover, it has been clinically confirmed that an artificial decrease in GABAergic activity had a positive effect on functional recovery [4].

A special role in the development of neurological deficits in acute and chronic ischemia and further functional recovery is played by the hemisphere contralateral to the actual lesion, since animal studies and clinical practice have well shown that neuronal connections after acute ischemia change not only in the damaged hemisphere of the brain, but also on the opposite side.

Due to the improvement of scientific methods, it has become possible to study changes in remote brain regions with local ischemic damage based on the concept of connectionism within the framework of microscopic (synapses), mesoscopic (homotopic brain regions) and macroscopic (thalamo-cortical connections) neuroplastic reactions.

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